

2. Abaxial leaf epidermis of *O. nivara* (x1 120), showing small and medium-sized papillae on the surface of epidermis, and rhombic stomatal complexes with 6-8 small papillae in subsidiary cells (indicated by arrows).

The third group included *O. sativa*, *O. nivara*, *O. rufipogon*, *O. longistaminata*, *O. lumaepatula*, *O. meridionalis*, *O. barthii*, and *O. schlechteri*. The abaxial leaf epidermis of these species was usually covered with large, medium-sized, and small papillae. In addition, more than four (usually 6-8) small papillae were found in guard cells or subsidiary cells of the stomatal complexes (Fig. 2). Most species in the second and third groups had rhombic stomatal complexes. This group is correlated to the morphologic *O. sativa* complex, except for *O. schlechteri*, which does not belong to any of the morphologic complexes.

These results largely agree with previous biosystematic studies of rice species that apply other methodologies, i.e., species within complexes have rather close relationships whereas those between complexes have a comparatively distant relationship. These results also show that leaf epidermal characters provide additional information for species identification in *Oryza*. ■

Genetics

Heterosis for physicochemical characters in rice

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Reports on heterosis for the physicochemical grain quality characters in rice are limited. We studied the heterotic manifestations in nine grain quality characters in 30 hybrids involving six parents—IR50, ADT37, ADT41, Duansan, TKM6, and ADT39. The hybrids were created by full diallel mating of these six parents.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications during the 1993-94 dry

season. Each genotype (parents and hybrids) was planted in three 3-m rows at 30- × 20-cm spacing. Observations were recorded for five randomly selected plants per replication.

Seeds were dehulled in a McGill sample sheller and milled in a Kett rice polisher. Cooking characters were measured as suggested by Juliano and Perez (1984). Amylose content was measured by the method of Juliano (1971), and the protein per grain was estimated by the method of Shenoy et al (1994).

The performance of hybrids over mid-parent (relative heterosis) and over the better parent (heterobeltiosis) was estimated following standard procedure (see table). The heterosis for

Summary of heterosis on nine physicochemical characters in hybrid rice.

Character	Relative heterosis		Heterobeltiosis		Top-ranking hybrids
	Range	Significant crosses ^a (no.)	Range	Significant crosses ^a (no.)	
Kernel length	-7.98 to 25.36	15	-18.60 to 19.65	8	ADT41/IR50 ADT39/ADT37 TKM6/ADT39 TKM6/ADT37
Kernel breadth	-40.63 to 18.06	15	-44.84 to 15.12	9	TKM6/ADT39 ADT41/IR50
Kernel L-B ratio	-12.68 to 68.27	10	-32.61 to 58.32	6	-
Kernel length after cooking	-21.34 to 26.43	14	-23.48 to 41.36	6	Duansan/ADT39 IR50/ADT37 ADT41/IR50
Kernel breadth after cooking	-9.26 to 31.89	14	-31.79 to 30.64	15	Duansan/ADT39 Duansan/IR50 ADT41/IR50
Linear elongation	-27.38 to 41.69	12	-37.79 to 33.82	11	ADT39/ADT41 IR50/Duansan ADT41/IR50
Elongation index	-55.84 to 59.74	13	-55.84 to 59.74	9	Duansan/ADT39 Duansan/ADT41 ADT41/IR50
Amylose (%)	-44.71 to 56.62	22	-44.78 to 42.60	19	ADT39/ADT37 TKM6/Duansan
Protein grain ⁻¹	-29.03 to 41.59	12	-42.11 to 32.69	7	ADT37/IR50 ADT39/Duansan ADT41/IR50

^aSignificant in the desirable direction.

the characters studied was considerably high and indicated the possibility of exploiting hybrid vigor for these traits. Among these hybrids, cross ADT41/ IR50 showed desirable heterobeltiosis for seven out of the nine

characters studied. The heterobeltiosis for this hybrid for kernel length was 1.23; kernel breadth, 5.70; kernel length-breadth ratio, 7.13; kernel length after cooking, -13.90; linear elongation, 8.70; elongation index, 22.97; amylose

content, 13.6; and protein per grain, 2.44. Duasan/ADT39 was promising for kernel length after cooking, kernel breadth after cooking, and elongation index. ■

Variability and heritability estimates of yield and yield components in some Nigerian lowland rice genotypes

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The essential aspects of most, if not all, breeding programs can be divided into three stages: assembly or creation of a pool of variable germplasm, selection of superior individuals from the pool, and use of selected material for creating new populations to be employed as either potential commercial varieties or the base for a new cycle of selection. Estimates of genetic variance and

heritabilities can be of value in all three stages.

We studied 10 early-duration and 12 medium-duration rice genotypes during the 1994-95 cropping season (Jul-Nov) at the University Experimental Research Station (UERS) to select promising genotypes. The experiment was laid out using a randomized complete block design with 4- × 3-m plots and three replicates for the medium-duration genotypes and four for the early-duration genotypes.

Observations were recorded on five randomly selected plants per replication. Mean (X), standard deviation (SD), phenotypic coefficient of variability (PCV) and genotypic

coefficient of variability (GCV), broad-sense heritability (h^2), and genetic advance as percentage of mean (GA%) were calculated for 12 traits (see table).

Considerable differences were observed for all the traits in both medium- and early-duration rice genotypes, indicating wide variability and room for improvement through selection. The PCV was generally higher than the GCV in both early- and medium-duration genotypes. The differences were low for days to 50% heading, however, and plant height in the medium-duration rice group and panicle weight, panicle length, and seed weight panicle⁻¹ in the early-duration group.

A moderate amount of variability (10-20%) was observed for days to 50% heading, plant height, panicles m⁻², panicle weight, number of seeds panicle⁻¹, and 1000-seed weight in the medium-duration category, whereas in the early-duration category plant height, tillers m⁻², panicles m⁻², branches m⁻², seed weight panicle⁻¹, and 1000-seed weight showed a moderate amount of variability.

The medium-duration rice genotypes had very low GCV for panicle length and branches panicle⁻¹, whereas the early- duration rice had very low GCV for days to 50% heading and panicle length. High h^2 as well as high GA%, for the medium- duration group was observed for days to 50% heading, plant height, 1000-seed weight, and tillers m⁻². Dry biological yield and seed yield had high GA% while in the early-duration genotypes, seed weight panicle⁻¹, dry biological yield, and seed yield had high h^2 and GA%. High h^2 coupled with high GA% indicates a predominance of additive gene effects. ■

Genetic parameters for 12 traits in selected lowland rice genotypes. University of Agriculture, Makurdi, Nigeria, 1994-95.

Trait	Mean (X)	Standard deviation	Genotypic coefficient of variation	Phenotypic coefficient of variation	Broad sense heritability (h^2)	Genetic advance as % of mean
<i>Medium duration</i>						
50% heading (d)	87.5	10.80	70.64	10.06	91.18	18.92
Plant height (cm)	78.8	8.15	65.68	11.91	74.64	18.33
Tillers m ⁻² (no.)	207.7	28.00	1376.46	24.77	52.00	26.57
Panicles m ⁻² (no.)	188.3	33.80	322.02	14.73	42.00	12.76
Panicle length (cm)	24.5	1.04	1.24	6.94	43.00	6.16
Branches panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	10.4	1.04	0.24	7.81	36.00	5.80
Panicle weight (g)	4.0	0.50	0.17	16.77	37.78	13.07
Seeds panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	142.2	19.30	127.27	17.13	21.00	7.42
Seed weight panicle ⁻¹ (g)	3.43	0.76	0.44	30.58	40.00	13.30
1000 weight (g)	25.8	2.85	9.95	13.35	83.00	22.87
Dry biomass yield (t ha ⁻¹)	5.21	0.97	2.46	43.05	49.00	43.52
Seed yield (t ha ⁻¹)	3.85	0.96	0.76	37.00	37.00	28.32
<i>Early duration</i>						
50% heading (d)	79.60	4.03	5.21	5.88	78.50	9.58
Plant height (cm)	73.40	6.22	8.25	10.68	59.61	13.11
Tillers m ⁻² (no.)	205.88	39.20	12.64	18.96	44.43	17.36
Panicles m ⁻² (no.)	173.80	25.55	10.53	19.13	30.31	11.94
Panicle length (cm)	23.79	1.10	3.12	8.00	15.19	2.50
Branches panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	9.36	1.18	12.80	15.46	68.50	21.82
Panicle weight (g)	3.10	0.59	15.04	43.49	11.97	10.72
Seeds panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	127.40	17.26	10.95	21.61	25.68	11.43
Seed weight panicle ⁻¹ (g)	2.89	0.61	19.11	30.62	38.95	24.57
1000 seed weight (g)	25.69	2.30	8.75	10.76	66.16	14.66
Dry biomass yield (t ha ⁻¹)	4.00	0.78	18.33	24.97	53.89	27.71
Seed yield (t ha ⁻¹)	3.00	0.78	30.14	39.69	57.67	47.15